

ON THE WAY OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN APPLICATION OF ELECTRONIC MARKETING STRATEGIES OPPORTUNITIES

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Annotation: *This article is about international tourism in Uzbekistan. Along with studying the Japanese experience in the development of Uzbekistan as a target unit of territory in the international tourism market electronic marketing strategies to ensure competitiveness bureau of electronic marketing "Uzbekistan", state tourism body developed at the level of private tourism organizations and e-marketing bureau responsible for the implementation. The activity develops the necessary proposals, detailing its main functions.*

Keywords: *Electronic media, email marketing, electronic marketing strategies for tourism, tourism of the region competitiveness, travel cycles.*

Uzbekistan is a leading tourist destination in the international tourism market

Tourism resources are enough to join the ranks of countries. We have every right to say. Because Uzbekistan is in the world interested in culture, customs and traditions, Amir Temur, Mirzo Hadiths such as Ulugbek, Abu Ali ibn Sino, Al Bukhari lived and worked

These figures have been recognized by the world community and are among the most important in his life. He longed to see this land it would not be an exaggeration to say that there are enough tourists here.

The same it should be noted that the country is a crossroads of the Great Silk Road. Recognize it as a way to advance in this international market attractiveness also gives him a competitive advantage, from such an achievement intended use is one of the most important marketing activities. It is known that Uzbekistan has its own national tourism brand and motto but it's just a diagram or sequence of words. So that these tourists do not develop in the subconscious and

consciousness of values, the graphic representation of these forms to be called a tourism "brand" only if it is reflected as a profitable finished tourism product possibly.

Uzbekistan as a tourist region in the international market to raise awareness led by Uzbektourism a lot of practical work is being done. Tradition to hold it every year

TITF (Tashkent International Tourism Fair) Tashkent International tourism fair, silk and spice festival and other cultural events, Bukhara, shown on the international TV channel Euronews, 30-60 seconds including Samarkand, Khiva and Tashkent videos highlight the tourism potential of Uzbekistan in the international community serves to demonstrate, albeit partially.

The Tashkent International Tourism Fair – “Tourism on the Silk Road” (TITF)– is the brightest and most large-scale event of the tourism industry of Uzbekistan and the entire Central Asian region.

The fair has been held since 1995 with the official support of the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO). Every year, the exhibition brings together professionals of the tourism business from all over the world.

In January 2019, President Sh. Mirziyoyev signed a Decree ” On additional measures for the accelerated development of tourism “, and issued a Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On measures to organize the annual Tashkent International Tourism Fair “Tourism on the Silk Road”, which determined the positive dynamics of its development in 2019. In particular, for 10 months of this year, the number of foreign tourists who visited our country amounted to 5.5 million people. This indicator is 26% higher compared to the same period last year (for 10 months of 2018 – 4.4 million people).²⁸

The official website of TITF-2020 was developed specifically for the online forum (www.uzbekistan.travel/titf-online/), which broadcast all conferences held on the Zoom platform. All participants and interested persons could directly participate in the sessions by registering on the website beforehand, or watch the conferences in real time.

More than 500 people from 32 countries, such as the USA, France, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Belgium, Thailand, Russia, Georgia, Kyrgyzstan, Japan, Spain, Canada, Italy, Switzerland, Egypt, etc. took part in the International Online Forum TITF-2020. During the 3 days of the Forum, about 4,000 people watched conference broadcasts in real time.

²⁸ <https://uzbekistan.travel/titf-2021/en/general-information/about-exhibition/>

Today TITF is the most effective information platform for promoting a tourist product and establishing business contacts. The exhibition provides an opportunity for the world's leading experts to exchange experience, discuss current problems of tourism, and present new directions. Leading experts announce the pricing policy, discuss current problems of tourism, open new directions.²⁹

But our In our opinion, the Internet and information technologies are developed in Uzbekistan. Doing business at the level of a tourist destination in the current century,

advertising, service marketing, country not used enough to give a complete impression of to this end, Uzbekistan as a solution to this problem its attractiveness through the creation of a regional brand and its promotion what it takes to develop an email marketing strategy we calculate.

Suggested Email Marketing Strategy 3 Sectors: Bureau of electronic marketing "Uzbekistan", state tourism functions performed by the body, private tourism organization email marketing in the region strategy of a potential tourist-tourist region – Uzbekistan, creating awareness - trip planning – booking give - visit - to the process of dreaming about the next trip special attention was paid to harmonious development.

First stage raising awareness as a tourist region of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the electronic marketing bureau "Uzbekistan", "Visit Uzbekistan!", "Open Uzbekistan!" title and "Feel the antiquity and hospitality" long-term (1-3 years) promotions under the slogan organization, travel blog, social networks, Google Map, Google Sites with interactive electronic maps such as Earth, Gis Meteo, You Tube and etc. text, images or text images, videos on websites marketing of potential tourists through the placement of materials to the Welcome Uzbekistan web portal.

Travel planning.³⁰ The main task of the electronic marketing bureau how to motivate a potential tourist to order depends on the effective use of tools. In this case, travel in planning (considered reliable in the eyes of tourists), of course, the official Internet portal of the region is the most convenient source of information is a web portal for planning a trip in front of tourists various technologies that facilitate (e.g. e-tourism, interactive using the possibilities of maps) and is available technology needs to be improved.

²⁹ <https://uzbekistan.travel/titf-2021/en/general-information/about-exhibition/>

³⁰ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Travel_plan

Email Marketing. The bureau plans to hold an annual meeting in the country. Sunday events, placement of the festival plan also on the website makes it more useful. It belongs to a government organization for the reception of tourists in agreement with government agencies with preparatory work, landscaping, changing the appearance of the city involved. Tourist organizations through electronic technologies. Quick, quality responses to questions from potential visitors or the Internet to pre-asked questions, which are an important part of sites answers can be found in the accessible section (FAQ).

Order. Potential tourist according to his needs and requirements or enough impressions and information about this tourist product.³¹ After receiving it, order it and buy it according to a specific plan decides to do. This stage from a potential tourist to a real tourist. The E-Marketing Bureau is a guest playing a defining role in the cycle referring to a web portal or specializing in a particular type of tourism order the selected service in 3 steps on the site and ease of payment using electronic means of payment must be created.

In general, nationwide ordered directly from the websites of tourist organizations it is impossible to buy the service.³² The main reason for this as the only online payment system in the country. It should be noted that the system is not created and does not solve this problem. Decided by the relevant government agencies, international payments online. At the time of its creation, it was a tourist enterprise that carried out payment transactions. It is necessary to develop mechanisms to encourage subjects. Private tourism organizations provide their travel services to the international market. Collaborate directly or indirectly with virtual organizations can be commercialized through.

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³¹ <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:452288/FULLTEXT01.pdf>

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